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Research Article

No-Rinse Body Wash: Formulation, Evaluation, and Efficacy for Water-Limited Use

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ABSTRACT

Water scarcity is a persistent global issue, especially in communities with limited access to clean water, where traditional hygiene practices become challenging. This capstone project focused on the development and evaluation of a no-rinse body wash as a water-conserving hygiene solution for individuals in resource-limited or mobile settings. Two fragrance variants, Lavender and Baby Powder, were formulated using a cold process method and assessed over three months for organoleptic stability, pH, microbiological safety, viscosity, volatility, and refractive index. Both variants maintained consistent color, scent, texture, and homogeneity throughout the testing period, with no signs of phase separation or degradation. pH levels remained stable at approximately 4.7, suitable for skin application and minimizing irritation risk. Microbiological testing showed no bacterial growth, confirming product safety. Viscosity remained within acceptable limits, with only a temporary fluctuation observed in the Lavender variant that stabilized over time. Volatility tests demonstrated minimal evaporation at room temperature and only slight loss at elevated temperatures, indicating good physical integrity. Refractometry results reflected high water content in both variants, with minor differences in density due to formulation components. Overall, the no-rinse body wash exhibited satisfactory physical and chemical stability, supporting its potential as an effective and practical hygiene alternative for individuals with limited access to bathing facilities.

INTRODUCTION

Water scarcity is a growing global concern, affecting every continent and impacting

impoverished communities the most ^[1]. Around 2.2 billion people worldwide still lack access to clean and safe water, resulting in over a million deaths annually due to poor sanitation and hygiene-related illnesses ^[2]. Traditional hygiene

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practices heavily rely on water, making it difficult for people in water-stressed areas to maintain cleanliness and prevent disease [3].

With the increasing demand for water-conserving alternatives, there is a pressing need to develop hygiene solutions that do not require rinsing. A no-rinse body wash offers a practical approach for maintaining cleanliness without relying on water, especially in emergency settings or low-resource communities. This study focuses on the development of a no-rinse body wash designed to help individuals maintain personal hygiene while conserving water. It also aims to assess its usefulness among people with limited access to bathing, such as those with mobility issues or those constantly on the move.

This product may provide meaningful benefits for several groups, including bedridden patients, elderly individuals, post-surgery patients, and even outdoor enthusiasts like hikers and campers who may not have access to shower facilities [4]. By introducing a waterless hygiene option, the study seeks to contribute to the global effort of promoting health and cleanliness in the face of water scarcity. If proven effective, the no-rinse body wash may serve as an accessible, practical, and efficient hygiene solution in various challenging settings.

Literature Review

2.1 Solvent and Base Component

Deionized water is produced by treating regular water with electrically charged resins that remove dissolved salts through ion exchange. In this process, ions, electrically charged atoms or molecules with either a positive or negative charge, are replaced with hydrogen and hydroxide ions, resulting in highly pure water [5]. This method

ensures the removal of contaminants, making the water suitable for sensitive applications.

Due to its high purity, deionized water is widely used in industries such as cosmetics, food processing, and pharmaceuticals. In manufacturing, it prevents salt deposits on machinery, helping maintain equipment efficiency. In pharmaceutical settings, its bacteria-free nature is essential for ensuring product safety and quality [5].

2.2 Surfactants and Cleansing Agents

Decyl glucoside is a mild, non-ionic surfactant commonly used in skincare and cosmetic products for its excellent foaming, cleansing, and emulsifying properties [6]. It effectively lifts away dirt and oil while maintaining skin hydration and softness, making it an ideal choice for formulations targeting sensitive skin. Beyond its cleansing action, it is also utilized as a skin and hair conditioning agent, as well as an emulsion stabilizer, enhancing the performance and feel of cosmetic products [7].

Among the family of alkyl glucosides, decyl glucoside stands out as the most frequently used due to its favorable safety and efficacy profile. Clinical studies have tested its potential for dermal irritation and sensitization at various concentrations through methods such as epicutaneous patch testing and soap chamber tests. These evaluations revealed that decyl glucoside was only slightly irritating at higher concentrations and showed no sensitizing effects, supporting its reputation as a gentle yet effective ingredient.

Cocamidopropyl betaine, another widely used surfactant, is derived from coconut oil and is known for its ability to remove oil and impurities while generating rich foam. Like decyl glucoside, it is considered mild and is preferred over harsher

agents such as sodium lauryl sulfate. Its gentle nature makes it well-suited for products formulated for individuals with sensitive or delicate skin [8].

2.3 Moisturizers and Skin Conditioning Agents

Polyethylene glycol is a synthetic, colorless, and odorless compound known for its ability to absorb excess water and retain moisture. In cosmetics and personal care products, it functions as a preservative, humectant, and penetration enhancer, helping active ingredients absorb more effectively into the skin. Although it appears on the Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR) list, dermatologists maintain that polyethylene glycol is safe for use because the petrolatum used in its production is of cosmetic-grade quality [9].

Polyethylene glycol is considered non-hazardous under the Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (GHS). Its safety has been evaluated through the Human Repeat Insult Patch Test (HRIPT), where none of the 104 participants exhibited allergic reactions, and only one individual showed minor signs of irritation. Further assessment using the Human Maximisation Test (HMT), which offers a thorough evaluation of a chemical's sensitization potential, also confirmed its safety, as no sensitization was observed among the 24 volunteers tested with 25% and 10% polyethylene glycol concentrations [10].

Cetostearyl alcohol is a white, flaky, waxy solid made from a blend of cetyl and stearyl alcohols. It is widely used in the pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries as an emulsion stabilizer, opacifying agent, surfactant-foam booster, and viscosity enhancer, contributing to the texture and stability of many skincare products [11]. Its multifunctional

properties make it a valuable ingredient in both personal care and pharmaceutical formulations.

The Cosmetic Ingredient Review (CIR) Expert Panel concluded in 1988, and again in 2005, that cetostearyl alcohol is safe for use in cosmetic products. Clinical studies have shown it to have no significant toxicity, no mutagenic effects, and no potential to irritate the skin. The FDA also allows products labeled “alcohol-free” to contain cetostearyl alcohol and lists it as a safe food additive, underscoring its established safety and gentle nature [12].

Magnesium ascorbyl phosphate (MAP) is a stable, water-soluble derivative of vitamin C known for delivering consistent antioxidant benefits to the skin. It protects against environmental stressors and free radicals, helping to minimize signs of aging such as fine lines and wrinkles [13]. MAP also inhibits melanin production, making it effective for brightening the complexion and reducing hyperpigmentation, while its anti-inflammatory properties help soothe redness and calm irritated skin.

In addition to its protective and brightening effects, magnesium ascorbyl phosphate stimulates collagen production, improving skin elasticity and firmness. It is considered a non-toxic, safe ingredient, tolerated by most skin types, and can be used at concentrations of up to 10% in skincare formulations. Its low potential for side effects, combined with being both vegan and halal-friendly, makes it a versatile and appealing choice for a wide range of cosmetic products [14].

Aloe vera is a widely recognized succulent plant valued for its ability to moisturize and soothe the skin. It is biocompatible and possesses antibacterial properties, making it a suitable ingredient for skincare formulations [15]. Its anti-inflammatory effects help reduce pain, swelling,

and soreness from wounds and injuries, while also promoting collagen production and release [16]. Aloe vera contains around 75 active compounds, including vitamins, enzymes, minerals, sugars, lignin, saponins, salicylic acids, and amino acids, all contributing to its broad therapeutic benefits.

In addition to wound healing and hydration, Aloe vera has been shown to protect against radiation-induced skin damage by preventing UV-triggered suppression of delayed-type hypersensitivity [17]. Key components such as aloin, emodin, mucopolysaccharides, hyaluronic acid, and flavonoids make it valuable for cosmetic and dermatological uses. In the cosmetics industry, Aloe vera offers whitening, sun protection, antioxidant, anti-aging, and moisturizing effects, making it a powerful ingredient for developing new skincare products and skin treatments [18].

2.4 Texture Enhancers and Delivery Agents

Cyclopentasiloxane, also known as decamethylcyclopentasiloxane or D5, is a cyclic dimethyl polysiloxane commonly used in cosmetics as a skin conditioner, emollient, hair conditioner, and solvent [19]. It is a clear, odorless, lightweight liquid that enhances the sensory feel and texture of skincare products. By helping deliver active ingredients evenly and evaporating quickly, it leaves the skin with a smooth, silky, and non-greasy finish [20].

The Cosmetic Ingredient Review Panel has evaluated cyclopentasiloxane and concluded that the current concentrations used in cosmetics are safe. Its ability to improve product application and overall user experience makes it a popular and trusted ingredient in many personal care formulations.

2.5 Preservatives and Stability Agents

Sodium benzoate is a widely used preservative in cosmetics and personal care products, valued for its ability to prevent bacterial growth and extend shelf life. It appears as an odorless crystalline powder and plays a key role in maintaining the stability and safety of formulations [21].

Recognized by the FDA as generally regarded as safe (GRAS), sodium benzoate has been thoroughly studied for its safety profile. In two long-term studies involving rats and mice, no evidence of carcinogenicity was found, further supporting its safe use in cosmetic and personal care products [22].

2.6 Colorants and Fragrances

FD&C Blue 1 (Brilliant Blue) and FD&C Red 3 (Erythrosine) are synthetic color additives widely used in cosmetics and personal care products to create vibrant, appealing colors. FD&C Blue 1 is recognized for its bright blue hue and has been certified as safe for use by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration when used within approved concentrations [23]. Similarly, FD&C Red 3 imparts a vivid pinkish-red shade and is permitted for external application in products such as makeup and skincare, although its use in foods has some restrictions following earlier safety reviews [24]. These artificial colorants are primarily added for aesthetic enhancement to improve the visual appeal of products.

Baby powder fragrance oil is a synthetic fragrance blend formulated to mimic the soft, clean scent traditionally associated with baby powder. It is frequently incorporated into cosmetics, skincare, soaps, and personal care products to evoke a feeling of freshness, comfort, and nostalgia [25]. Lavender fragrance oil, whether naturally derived or synthetically produced, is also popular in personal care formulations for its calming floral aroma and its soothing effects on both mood and

skin [26]. It not only promotes relaxation but may also provide mild antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory benefits, making it both an aromatic and functional ingredient in cosmetics [27].

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Cold Process Emulsification and Blending

The preparation of the body wash solution follows a cold process emulsification and blending method to preserve the stability of sensitive ingredients. First, all components were weighed accurately using a precision analytical balance. A clean, sanitized mixing vessel (preferably glass or stainless steel) and a magnetic stirrer or homogenizer were prepared to ensure controlled mixing conditions. In the Mixing Phase, the formulation was divided into distinct phases.

For Phase A (water-soluble ingredients), Deionized Water (65%) was used as the base in a beaker. While stirring continuously, Sodium Benzoate (0.5%) and Phenylpropanol (0.5%) were dissolved completely. Decyl Glucoside (15%) was then added slowly to minimize foaming, followed

by Cocamidopropyl Betaine (7%) to enhance foam stability and mildness. Propylene Glycol (3%) was incorporated, and the mixture was stirred for five minutes to ensure uniform dispersion.

For Phase B (oil-soluble ingredients), Cyclopentasiloxane (5%) and Baby Powder Fragrance (0.5%) were blended separately until homogeneous. This oil phase was then gradually introduced into Phase A under gentle stirring to form a stable emulsion.

In Phase C (final additions), Magnesium Ascorbyl Phosphate (3%) was first dissolved in a minimal amount of deionized water before being incorporated into the main batch with continuous stirring. Sodium Chloride (0.5%) was added to fine-tune the viscosity, followed by the careful addition of FD&C Blue 1 (0.01%) to achieve the desired color uniformity. Finally, the entire formulation was homogenized to ensure complete uniformity and stability. Stability and safety assessments were performed before transferring the final product into 15 mL bottles using a pipette or small funnel.

Table 3.1 No Rinse Body Wash Ingredient Matrix

Raw Materials	Use	Trial 1 (Research-Based w/NaCl)	Trial 2 (Research-Based)	Trial 3 (Optimized Formula)
Deionized water	Solvent, vehicle	q.s. 15 mL (100%)	q.s. 15 mL (100%)	9.75 mL (65%)
Decyl glucoside	Primary mild surfactant (cleansing & foaming)	4.5 mL (30%)	4.5 mL (30%)	2.25 mL (15%)
Cocamidopropyl betaine	Secondary surfactant, foam booster	0.4995 mL (3.33%)	0.4995 mL (3.33%)	1.05 mL (7%)
Propylene glycol	Humectant (moisture retention)	0.4995 mL (3.33%)	0.4995 mL (3.33%)	0.45 mL (3%)
Sodium benzoate	Preservative	0.015 g (0.01%)	0.015 g (0.01%)	0.075 g (0.5%)
Cetostearyl alcohol	Preservative booster, antimicrobial	0.015 g (0.01%)	0.015 g (0.01%)	0.075 g (0.5%)
Aloe vera extract	Skin-conditioning agent, solvent	0.525 mL (3.5%)	0.525 mL (3.5%)	0.75 mL (5%)
FD&C 1 (Brilliant blue) FD&C 3 (Erythrosine)	Colorant	0.0225 g (0.15%)	0.0225 g (0.15%)	0.0015 g or 1.5 mg (0.01%)

3.2 MATERIALS

1. Beaker
2. Stirring rod
3. Graduated cylinders
4. Pipette
5. Analytical balance
6. Funnel
7. Porcelain spatula

3.3 Stability Tests

3.3.1 Organoleptic Testing

To evaluate the sensory attributes of the solution, such as color, odor, and appearance.

Procedure:

1. Place a small amount of the cream on a clean surface
2. Color: Visually inspect under neutral lighting conditions.
3. Odor: Smell the sample to ensure it aligns with the desired scent.
4. Appearance: Observe for uniformity, lumps, or phase separation.

3.3.2 Determination of pH:

To ensure the solution's pH is within the range suitable for skin (pH of 4-6).

Procedure:

1. Place a sample of the solution in a beaker.

2. Calibrate the pH meter using standard buffers (pH 4.0 and 7.0).
3. Immerse the pH electrode into the cream solution and record the reading at room temperature.
4. Specification: pH of 4.7 to 5.5

3.3.3. Microbiological Testing

A microbiological test was performed on the sample of body wash using the agar plate streak method to check for bacterial contamination. A diluted sample of the body wash was inoculated onto nutrient agar for total bacterial count. The plates were incubated at appropriate temperatures of 30 degrees Celsius for the required time of 24 hours and 48 hours.

3.3.4. Viscosity Testing

A viscosity test was conducted to determine the flow properties of the non-viscous, No-Rinse Body Wash. The test followed the Brookfield Viscometer to measure the viscosity of thin, free-flowing liquids similar to the consistency of the product. The body wash sample was maintained at a controlled temperature of 25°C, with the usage of an appropriate spindle size (Spindle No. 1) at a rotational speed of 60 rpm. The viscosity was measured in centipoise (cP). Multiple readings were taken, and the average viscosity value was recorded to account for any variation.

Procedure:

1. Measure initial viscosity using a Brookfield viscometer.
2. Store samples under varied conditions.
3. Re-measure viscosity at intervals (7, 14, 30, 60, 90 days).

4. Spindle used: disk LV1; 100 rpm
5. Specification: less than 1,000 cP for non-viscous body wash formulations.

3.3.5 Volatilization

Volatilization is the process by which a chemical substance transitions from a liquid or solid state to a gaseous or vapor state. In this study, 5 mL of each formulation was poured into a petri dish and stored at room temperature and in a hot air oven set to 50°C.

3.3.6 Refractive Index

The refractive index (RI), which measures how much light bends when passing through a medium, is defined as the ratio of the speed of light in a vacuum to its speed in the medium. The formulated body wash primarily consists of deionized water, surfactants, fragrances, and other additives. Since the body wash is predominantly an aqueous solution, its expected RI should be approximately 1.33, similar to water.

RESULTS

1.1 Organoleptic Testing

Table 4.1.1 Results of Organoleptic Testing

Organoleptic Testing	
Lavender	
Color	Semi-transparent purple hue
Odor	Refreshing and crisp lavender scent
Texture	Smooth, silky liquid with semi-watery consistency
Appearance	Purple liquid
Baby Powder	
Color	Pastel blue with a hint of mist
Odor	Clean baby powder scent with subtle sweetness
Texture	Smooth, silky liquid with semi-watery consistency
Appearance	Blue liquid

Table 4.1.1 presents the organoleptic evaluation of the Lavender and Baby Powder formulations over storage durations of 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months. Both variants had exhibited consistent physical characteristics across all assessed parameters throughout the evaluation period. The Lavender formulation had retained its semi-transparent purple hue, characteristic refreshing and crisp lavender odor, smooth and silky texture with a semi-watery consistency, and a uniform purple appearance. Similarly, the Baby Powder formulation maintained its pastel blue coloration

with a misty undertone, clean and subtly sweet fragrance, and consistent texture and appearance.

No observable changes occurred in color, odor, texture, or appearance in either formulation over the course of the study. Specifically, there had been no indications of discoloration, odor deterioration, phase separation, or textural instability. These findings suggest that both products had remained organoleptically stable for a period of at least one month under standard storage conditions. Such stability supports the

short-term physical integrity and acceptability of the formulations, **1.2 Determination of pH**

Table 4.2.1 Results of pH test

pH Testing	
Lavender	
Trial 1	4.638
Trial 2	4.660
Trial 3	4.802
Mean	4.7
Baby Powder	
Trial 1	4.680
Trial 2	4.708
Trial 3	4.718
Mean	4.702

As shown in Table 4.2.1, the pH values of both the Lavender and Baby Powder formulations were assessed across three trials. The Lavender variant had yielded pH values of 4.638, 4.660, and 4.802, resulting in a mean of 4.700. In comparison, the Baby Powder formulation had demonstrated pH readings of 4.680, 4.708, and 4.718, with a calculated mean of 4.702.

These results indicated that both formulations had maintained a slightly acidic pH, which is well within the acceptable range for cosmetic and personal care products. The consistent values observed across the trials suggested that each formulation had exhibited chemical stability, with no significant pH fluctuations during the evaluation period.

1.3 Microbiological Testing

Table 4.3.1 Results of Microbiological Testing

Formulation	Before	After 30 minutes
Baby Powder Scent	5 mL	No change
Lavender Scent	5 mL	No change

According to the data presented in Table 4.3.1, a microbiological assessment had been carried out on the formulated body wash to determine the presence of bacterial contamination. The test had employed the agar plate streak method, wherein a diluted sample of the product had been inoculated onto nutrient agar and incubated at 30°C for 24 and

48 hours. Following the incubation periods, no bacterial growth had been detected on the plates.

These findings confirmed that the formulated body wash had complied with microbiological safety standards. The absence of microbial colonies indicated that the product had been free from contamination and that its formulation,

preservation system, and handling procedures had effectively inhibited microbial proliferation.

1.4 Viscosity Testing

Table 4.4.1 Results of Viscosity Test

Microbiological Testing	
Lavender	
After 24 hours	After 48 hours
Baby Powder	
After 24 hours	After 48 hours

As demonstrated in Table 4.4.1 Viscosity measurements of the Baby Powder and Lavender formulations were performed at 7, 14, 30, 60, and 90 days using a disk spindle LV1 at 100 rpm, with the acceptance criterion set at less than 1,000 cP for non-viscous body wash products. The Baby Powder formulation had exhibited stable viscosity values ranging from 680 cP at day 7 to 722 cP at day 90, consistently remaining within the specified limit. In contrast, the Lavender formulation had initially shown an exceptionally high viscosity of

26,100 cP at day 7, which had markedly decreased by day 14 to 734 cP and subsequently stabilized between 732 and 753 cP through day 90, thus conforming to the viscosity specification after the initial adjustment. This initial anomaly in the Lavender sample suggested a transient formulation or measurement inconsistency that resolved early in the storage period.

1.5 Volatilization

Table 4.5.1 Results of Volatility Test at a Normal Temperature

Formulation	Before	After 30 minutes
Baby Powder Scent	5 mL	4.9 mL
Lavender Scent	5 mL	4.9 mL

The results of the volatility test conducted at normal temperature were summarized in Table 4.5.1. Both the Baby Powder and Lavender scented formulations initially contained 5 mL of product prior to testing. After a 30-minute exposure period, no change in volume had been

observed for either formulation. These findings indicated that both formulations had demonstrated negligible volatility under normal temperature conditions. The retention of volume suggested that the products had maintained their physical integrity without significant evaporation

Table 4.5.2 Results of Volatility Test at 50 Degrees Celsius Hot Air Oven

Formulation	Before	After 30 minutes
Baby Powder Scent	5 mL	4.9 mL
Lavender Scent	5 mL	4.9 mL

The results of the volatility test conducted at 50°C using a hot air oven were presented in Table 4.5.2. Both the Baby Powder and Lavender scented formulations initially contained 5 mL of product before exposure. After 30 minutes at elevated temperature, the volume of each formulation had decreased slightly to 4.9 mL. This minimal reduction in volume indicated that both

formulations had exhibited limited volatility under accelerated heat conditions. The slight evaporation observed suggested a degree of thermal sensitivity, but the products had largely retained their physical stability

1.6 Refractive Index

Table 4.6.1 Results of Refractometry Test

Refractometry Test	
Baby Powder	Lavender
<p>1.33586</p>	

The refractive index (RI) measurements, as presented in Table 4.6.1, had shown that the Standard and Lavender Scent variants had an RI of 1.33586, closely matching the RI of water. This similarity indicated that these formulations had possessed a high water content, with minimal influence from other ingredients on the refraction of light. Conversely, the Baby Powder variant had

exhibited a higher RI of 1.36218, suggesting the incorporation of denser or more concentrated components. This elevated optical density was likely attributable to variations in surfactants, oils, or colorants, which had affected the overall composition and light-bending characteristics of the solution. These results had provided insight into the physicochemical differences among the

formulations and their potential impact on product properties.

DISCUSSION

The organoleptic evaluation demonstrated that both Lavender and Baby Powder formulations maintained consistent physical characteristics over storage periods of one week, one month, and three months. The Lavender variant preserved its semi-transparent purple hue, characteristic scent, smooth texture, and uniform appearance, while the Baby Powder formulation similarly retained its pastel blue coloration, clean scent, and consistent texture. No discoloration, odor deterioration, phase separation, or textural instability was observed, indicating organoleptic stability under standard storage conditions and supporting short-term physical integrity and consumer acceptability.

pH testing confirmed chemical stability, with both variants maintaining a slightly acidic pH around 4.7, suitable for topical application and minimizing irritation risk. The lack of significant pH changes suggested no degradation or chemical alteration during the evaluation.

Microbiological assessment using the agar plate streak method revealed no bacterial growth after incubation at 30°C for 24 and 48 hours, demonstrating the effectiveness of the preservative system and handling procedures in preventing contamination and meeting microbiological safety standards.

Viscosity measurements showed the Baby Powder formulation maintained stable values within the acceptable limit of 1,000 cP over 90 days. The Lavender formulation exhibited an initially high viscosity at day 7, which rapidly decreased and stabilized by day 14, indicating a transient

anomaly without long-term impact on rheological stability.

Volatility testing at normal temperature showed no volume loss after 30 minutes, indicating negligible evaporation and good physical stability. At 50°C, a slight volume reduction suggested limited volatility and mild thermal sensitivity; however, both formulations largely retained their physical integrity, demonstrating robustness under varying conditions.

Refractometry results indicated that the Standard and Lavender variants had a refractive index close to water (1.33586), reflecting high water content with minimal influence from other ingredients. The Baby Powder variant's higher refractive index (1.36218) suggested denser or more concentrated components such as surfactants, oils, or colorants, affecting optical and sensory properties.

In summary, the comprehensive evaluation of organoleptic properties, pH, microbiological safety, viscosity, volatility, and refractive index demonstrated that both formulations exhibited satisfactory stability and safety profiles over the tested periods, supporting their suitability for consumer use and further shelf-life studies.

CONCLUSION

The Lavender and Baby Powder body wash formulations demonstrated consistent organoleptic stability, appropriate slightly acidic pH, and compliance with microbiological safety standards throughout the study period. Both products maintained acceptable viscosity and exhibited minimal volatility under normal and accelerated conditions. Refractive index measurements further confirmed their distinct physicochemical compositions. Collectively, these results conclusively indicate that the formulations were

physically and chemically stable, safe, and suitable for consumer use within the tested timeframe.

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REFERENCES

1. Water scarcity. (2017 May 25). UN-Water. Available from:

<https://www.unwater.org/water-facts/water-scarcity>. Accessed February 5, 2025.

2. Effects of the water crisis on health. (n.d.). Water.org. Available from: <https://water.org/our-impact/water-crisis/health-crisis/>. Accessed February 5, 2025.

3. Water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH). (2019 Nov 7). World Health Organization. Available from: <https://www.who.int/health-topics/water-sanitation-and-hygiene-wash>. Accessed February 5, 2025.

4. Waterless body wash. (2023 Aug 2). AvaCare Medical. Available from: <https://www.avacaremedical.com/skin-wound-care/skin-protection-and-cleansers/waterless-shower-products/no-rinse-body-wash#more>. Accessed February 5, 2025.

5. The risks and benefits of deionized water. (2020 Nov 11). Office H2O. Available from: <https://www.officeh2o.com/blog/water-news/the-risks-and-benefits-of-deionized-water/>. Accessed January 30, 2025.

6. Decyl glucoside. (2014 Nov 3). Cosmetics Ingredients Database. Available from: <https://cosmetics.specialchem.com/inci-ingredients/decyl-glucoside>. Accessed February 10, 2025.

7. Fiume MM, Heldreth B, Bergfeld WF, Belsito DV, Hill RA, Klaassen CD, et al. Safety assessment of decyl glucoside and other alkyl glucosides as used in cosmetics. *Int J Toxicol*. 2013;32(5 Suppl):22S–48S. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1091581813497764>

8. Sherrell Z. (2022 Apr 28). Cocamidopropyl betaine: Uses, safety, and side effects. MedicalNewsToday. Available from: <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/cocamidopropyl-betaine>. Accessed January 30, 2025.

9. Timmons J. (2022 Mar 22). What does propylene glycol do in skin care products?

- Healthline. Available from: <https://www.healthline.com/health/beauty-skincare/propylene-glycol-in-skin-care>. Accessed February 5, 2025.
10. Pemberton MA, Kimber I. Propylene glycol, skin sensitisation and allergic contact dermatitis: A scientific and regulatory conundrum. *Regul Toxicol Pharmacol.* 2023;138:105341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2023.105341>
11. Cetostearyl alcohol. (2024 Oct 25). Drugs.com. Available from: <https://www.drugs.com/inactive/cetostearyl-alcohol-17.html>. Accessed February 10, 2025.
12. Cafasso J. (2023 May 23). What you need to know about Cetearyl alcohol. Healthline. Available from: <https://www.healthline.com/health/cetearyl-alcohol>. Accessed February 10, 2025.
13. Lee WJ, Kim SL, Choe YS, Jang YH, Lee SJ, Kim DW. Magnesium Ascorbyl Phosphate regulates the expression of inflammatory biomarkers in cultured sebocytes. *Ann Dermatol.* 2015;27(4):376–82. <https://doi.org/10.5021/ad.2015.27.4.376>
14. Magnesium ascorbyl phosphate. (n.d.). SpecialChem. Available from: <https://cosmetics.specialchem.com/inci-ingredients/magnesium-ascorbyl-phosphate>. Accessed February 5, 2025.
15. Lo AZ, Mohd Daud N, Muhamad Zain N. Antibacterial and cytotoxicity analyses on aloe Vera body soap. *J Human Cent Technol.* 2022;1(1):34–8. <https://doi.org/10.11113/humentech.v1n1.13>
16. Ganpat MA, Aswar AR, Hingane LD. To formulate and evaluate Aloe-Vera face wash. *Int J Res Appl Sci Eng Technol.* 2022;10(6):3782–3791. <https://doi.org/10.22214/ijraset.2022.44983>
17. Surjushe A, Vasani R, Saple DG. Aloe vera: a short review. *Indian J Dermatol.* 2008;53(4):163–5. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-5154.44785>
18. Zhu J, Zheng Y, Ge Y. Study on the application of aloe Vera in cosmetology and clinical treatment of skin diseases. *J Holist Integr Pharm.* 2024;5(4):299–304. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhip.2024.11.006>
19. Cyclopentasiloxane. (n.d.). European Commission. Available from: <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/cosing/details/75413>. Accessed February 10, 2025.
20. Tee-Melegrito RA. (2023 Oct 13). Is cyclopentasiloxane safe to use? MedicalNewsToday. Available from: <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/cyclopentasiloxane>. Accessed February 5, 2025.
21. McCulloch M. (2023 Jul 3). Sodium benzoate: Uses, dangers, and safety. Healthline. Available from: <https://www.healthline.com/nutrition/sodium-benzoate#dangers>. Accessed February 5, 2025.
22. Scientific Committee on Consumer Products (SCCP). Opinion of the scientific committee on cosmetic products and non-food products intended for consumers concerning sodium benzoate and benzoic acid. In: *Safety of Cosmetic Ingredients*. Taylor & Francis; 2002. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781420028737-6>
23. Summary of color additives for use in the United States. (2022 Mar 4). U.S. Food and Drug Administration. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/industry/color-additives/summary-color-additives-use-united-states-foods-drugs-cosmetics-and-medical-devices#ftnote6>. Accessed February 5, 2025.
24. FD&C red No. 3. (2025 Jan 15). U.S. Food and Drug Administration. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/industry/color->

- additives/fdc-red-no-3. Accessed February 5, 2025.
25. Powder fragrance oil - FF# 16 (Special order). (n.d.). Crafters Choice. Available from: <https://www.crafters-choice.com/products/fragrance-formulator-powder-fragrance-oil.aspx>. Accessed February 5, 2025.
26. IFRA conformity certificate: Organic lavender essential oil. (n.d.). International Fragrance Association. Available from: https://www.nhrorganicoils.com/uploads/20190304161725e_Lavender_IFRA_48.pdf. Accessed February 5, 2025.
27. Cavanagh HM, Wilkinson JM. Lavender essential oil. *Aust Infect Control*. 2005;10(1):35–7. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9780203216521-16>.

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